

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "The animal welfare cost of meat: evidence from a survey of hypothetical scenarios among Belgian consumers"

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "The animal welfare cost of meat: evidence from a survey of hypothetical scenarios among Belgian consumers"^[1]. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Romain Espinosa](#)

2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 2	80	2.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Romain Espinosa

Bruers (2023) emerged as a third concomitant proposal to economically value animal welfare. The paper starts from the idea that animals, while having preferences, cannot express willingness-to-pay (WTP) or willingness-to-accept (WTA) related to changes that could affect their welfare status. Policymakers and social planners thus lack appropriate measures to estimate the welfare impact of a policy on animals (measures that we could use in benefit-cost analyses for instance). To address this problem, the author proposes to elicit humans' WTP/WTA to experience an animal's life (focusing on farmed animals). He argues that these outcomes reflect the external animal welfare costs, i.e., the welfare burden imposed on animals, which is distinct from the altruistic concerns

that humans experience when they impact animals. In this setup, a positive WTP to avoid experiencing an animal's life would reflect the belief that a farmed animal's life is not worth living.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This study explores animal welfare costs of meat consumption, using stated preference methods from a sample of Belgians to elicit willingness to pay (WTP) and willingness to accept (WTA) measures for animal welfare. While the theoretical framework is robust and the research attempts to mitigate several biases, the small sample size and reliance on open-ended WTP elicitation limit reliability. The study provides valuable insights into relative animal welfare costs and consumer preferences, serving as a foundation for future research.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Romain Espinosa	Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Rating category	Comments [in footnotes]	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴		80	(70, 90)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	[⁶]	70	(65, 75)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	[⁸]	90	(85, 95)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁹	[¹⁰]	65	(60, 70)
Logic & communication ¹¹	[¹²]	90	(85, 95)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹³	[¹⁴]	80	(75, 85)
Real-world relevance ^{15, 16}	[¹⁷]	80	(70, 90)

Relevance to global priorities ^{18, 19}	[²⁰]	80	(70, 90)
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Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.5	(2.0, 3.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 	

Evaluation manager's discussion

Note — 4 Feb 2025: The notes below are brief. We may to return to provide further discussion. However, this may not be necessary, as the evaluations and authors' responses include extensive context and discussion.

Why we chose this paper

From our prioritization notes:

Topic wise, this is a central question for policy.

the core experiment seems a top innovation and with some potential to adopt more widely and potentially improve.

[Raised some questions about the methods and their interpretation]

Early rigorous example of quantifying animal welfare concerns in a way that can be practically applied.

Further discussion of this paper could motivate people to do larger-scale survey-based work on this.

Evaluation process/COI

The field of animal welfare economics is small. Both the evaluators and relevant members of The Unjournal team have interacted with the author in the past, e.g., in small conferences. There was some productive back-and-forth discussion with the author, as seen in his responses.

References

1. Bruers, S. (2023). The animal welfare cost of meat: evidence from a survey of hypothetical scenarios among Belgian consumers. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 12(3), 324–341.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2022.2138980>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6.

This paper significantly contributes to the discussion on animal welfare valuation by showing some limits of anthropocentric valuation including his own approach. The author recognizes that his method is not reliable to obtain accurate estimates of the welfare of animals. However, it makes a great contribution by underlining the numerous issues that make such approaches unreliable (e.g., the perception of the animal's capacity to experience the world, the perception of the animal's farming conditions, hypothetical biases, outliers, and exclusion criteria).

The work also contains numerous limitations, and most of them are recognized by the author himself. The main (and most standard) limitation is the hypothetical nature of the survey: participants do not face real incentives, which might lead to underestimating or overestimating the welfare burden of our diet imposed on animals. One of the most intrinsic limits concerns the difficulty for lay people (and humans in general) to project themselves into the lives of animals of other species. One can be indeed ignorant about the needs, the perception of the world, the cognition, etc. of other species, such that estimating their welfare is a daunting task. In addition, humans can also be ignorant about the rearing conditions in "conventional" farms, making the estimates even more uncertain. Ultimately, the layers of complexity (unusual survey, ignorance about other species, uncertainty about rearing conditions) add up and make the point estimates hard to rely on.↵

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

8. The paper brings valuable insight into the broader research question of how to get monetary valuations of animal welfare using the tools and approaches of economics. ↵

9. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↵

10.

Within the limits that the author himself recognizes, and with the exception of the cultured meat questions, the methods are valid, reasonable, and well-justified. From a theoretical perspective, the measure of the human's perception of the welfare of the animal is well defined: it corresponds to the change in private endowment that makes the human indifferent between living and not living the animal's life on top of his own life. From an empirical perspective, the author estimates it by considering several challenges, including (i) that some participants might have positive or negative perceptions of the welfare of the animal (i.e., the author uses a first-stage question to elicit the preferred pill), (ii) WTA/WTP framing might alter the results, (iii) outliers could lead to extremely high average WTP/WTA, (iv) some participants might have very low confidence in this unusual exercise, and (v) there might be some intrinsic (dis)utility in living an animal's life.

The work also contains numerous limitations, and most of them are recognized by the author himself. The main (and most standard) limitation is the hypothetical nature of the survey: participants do not face real incentives, which might lead to underestimating or overestimating the welfare burden of our diet imposed on animals. One of the most intrinsic limits concerns the difficulty for lay people (and humans in general) to project themselves into the lives of animals of other species. One can be indeed ignorant about the needs, the perception of the world, the cognition, etc. of other species, such that estimating their welfare is a daunting task. In addition, humans can also be ignorant about the rearing conditions in "conventional" farms, making the estimates even more uncertain. Ultimately, the layers of complexity (unusual survey, ignorance about other species, uncertainty about rearing conditions) add up and make the point estimates hard to rely on. [↵](#)

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

12. The paper is well-written and easy to understand both for academics and less-specialized readers. [↵](#)
13.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

14. I did not find an online repository for data and code. [↵](#)

15.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

⇐

16.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ⇐

17. Because the author recognizes that the method might not be reliable for empirical estimation, the usefulness might be limited for practitioners (other than to prevent them from replicating such approaches). ⇐

18. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ⇐

19.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ⇐

20. The paper has a high relevance to global priorities given the prevalence of animal factory farming nowadays. ⇐

References

1. Bruers, S. (2023). The animal welfare cost of meat: evidence from a survey of hypothetical scenarios among Belgian consumers. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 12(3), 324–341.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2022.2138980> ⇐